

MUSIC THERAPY

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Music Therapy is an established health profession in which music is used within a therapeutic relationship to address to physical, emotional, cognitive and social needs of individuals. After assessing the strength and needs of each client, the qualified music therapist provides the indicated treatment including creating, singing, moving to and/or listening to music. Through musical involvement in therapeutic context, clients, abilities are strengthened and transfer to other areas of their lives.

Music has frequently been used as a therapeutic agent from the ancient times. Music is a kind of yoga system through the medium of sonorous sound, which acts upon the human organism, awakens, and develops their proper functions to extent of self-realization; this is the ultimate goal of Hindu philosophy and religion. Melody is the keynote of Indian Music. The 'Raga' is the basis of melody various 'Ragas' been found to the very effective in curing many diseases.

The rules of musical therapy in India can be treated back to ancient Hindu Mythology, Vedic texts and local folk tradition. It is very possible the music therapy has been used for hundreds of years in the Indian culture.

Research in music therapy supports its effectiveness in many areas such as overall physical rehabilitation and facilitating movement increasing people`s motivation to become engaged in their treatment, providing emotional support for clients and their families and providing an outlet for expression of feelings.

Dr. Khandekar has paramount experience in treatment of patients with music therapy and has a large number of patients who have been benefited from music therapy treatment under his guidance from Blood pressure, Diabetes, Insomnia and other CNS nervous disorders etc. He is the one of the best-qualified music therapist in India.

Music therapy is used in medical disorders like heart disease, Neurological disorders, Stroke , Dementia , Amnesia, Aphasia , It is also used is psychiatric disorders like, schizophrenia, Depression etc.

PRINCIPALS OF MUSIC THERAPY

Music therapy in not the subject of an article only the entire subject is now in the experimental and implementation large and data are rapidly accumulating, and the ancient system is gradually being transformed in to a modern science. It was experienced by people that Indian Classical 'Ragas' have been acclaimed to have healing effects. They stimulate the brain ease tension and

remove fatigue. The effect of music therapy may be immediate or slow, depending upon numbers of factors like the subject, his mental condition, environment and the type of music, selected for having the desired effect. Music therapy largely depends on individual's needs and taste. The use of music as therapy is based on scientific and clinical approach and has to be used with great care and deep study of the nature of illness. We can call it "The study of Individual modality theory". Before using music as therapy it must ascertain which type of music is to be used. The Concept of music therapy is dependent on correct intonation and right use of the basic elements of music.

Music helps in the treatment of actual diseases in the following manners:

- 1 One obvious use of music is that of a sedative. It can replace the administration of tranquilizers, or at least reduce the dosage of tranquilizers.
- 2 Music increases the metabolic activities within the human body. It accelerates the respiration, influences the internal section, improves the muscular activities and as such affects the central nervous system and circulatory system of the listener and the performer.

PRENATAL MUSIC THERAPY

Music therapy can play an important role during pregnancy. At just 16 weeks, a fetus is able to hear their mother's speech as well as singing, Through technologies, such as ultrasound, health care professionals are able to absorb the movement of the unborn child responding to musical stimuli .

Prenatal music therapy has three main benefits:

- 1 **Prenatal stress relief-** Pregnant women may high levels of stress, which can negatively affect the baby. This technique is useful in helping reduce the mother's level of stress and prepare her for the birth of her child.
- 2 **Maternal- fetal bonding-** Strengthening the bond between mother and fetus is through music therapy. Music stimulate helps to develop the fetus's nervous system, structurally and functionally.
- 3 **Prenatal Language Development-** Music is said to be the unborn child's beginning of language learning. It can be considered as a pre-linguistic that prepares the auditory sensory system to listen, combine and produce language sounds.

MUSIC THERAPY AND CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

Music therapy can be particularly useful when working with children with autism due to the non-verbal, non-threatening nature of medium. Studies have shown that children with autism have difficulties with joint attention symbolic communication and sharing the positive effect, use of music therapy has demonstrated improvements of socially accept-able behaviors. Successful therapy involves long term individual intervention tailored to each child's needs. Passing and

sharing instruments, music and movement games, learning to listen and singing greeting and improvised stories are just a few ways music therapy can improve a child`s social interaction.

Hearing is physical and listening is psychological. Both are vital to our communication skills, establishing good relationship, socializing with everyone and learning intuitiveness, out of the 12 cranial nerves, 10 are linked to the ear, indicating the importance of the musical sound to our nervous system.

For the best results for hearing we must listen to the music only in a relaxed position like lying down or sitting posture when we are alone or in privacy. It will be more effective if the music is heard with a headphone. The sounds and tones of the music must be observed and aligned into our mind and body, listen to the music for 20- 30 minutes every day for at least 6 to 8 weeks before going to bed.

CONCLUSION

In today`s hectic and stressful life schedule, the only hope is music therapy, which gives peace and relaxation. This therapy cures physic and mental diseases without any side effects. As it is a known fact that stress is the root cause of all diseases this therapy helps a man to remove the stress and keeps all the diseases away. In globalized world, people still are not known to this therapy and its advantages. The need of the time is to make people aware of the advantages of music therapy. In this particular field, more research possibilities are yet to trace. We can hope this therapy in future will become a popular therapy.

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